

Fear of Missing Out (FOMO) in the Digital Age: Explore The Impacts of Mental Health and Productivity among IT Professionals

TABLE I. VARIABLES AND INDICATORS

Code	Question	Ref
FoMO		
FM1	I am afraid of missing out on profitable trend experiences.	[4] [6] [9]
FM2	I'm afraid that others might get the profitable trend experience without me.	
FM3	It is important to me to know about a trend that other people are going to experience.	
FM4	It's important to me to be involved in a trend that other people will experience.	
FM5	I'm afraid of not knowing what trends are going to happen to other people.	
FM6	I get anxious when I miss out on a trend that other people are going to experience.	
Extrinsic Reward		
ER1	I feel more accepted by my friends if I follow the existing trends.	[4] [2] [3]
ER2	I feel more approved by the people around me if I follow the existing trends.	
ER3	I feel more involved in social circles if I follow the existing trends.	
ER4	I feel comfortable with other people if they follow the existing trend.	
Internet Use Expectancies		
IUE1	I use social media to distract myself.	[3]
IUE2	I use social media to avoid loneliness.	[1]
IUE3	I use social media to feel pleasure.	[9]
IUE4	I use social media to feel satisfied.	
State-FoMO		
SF1	I am constantly online so as not to miss anything.	[2] [3] [10]]
SF2	It is important for me to have my say on current issues on my online social networks (videos, pictures, posts, etc.).	
SF3	I am afraid of not knowing the development of trends on my social media sites.	
SF4	I constantly check my phone to keep up with any trends and news.	
Information Overload		
IO1	I am often distracted by the overwhelming amount of information available to me in making business decisions.	[4] [14]] [11]]
IO2	I feel exhausted by the amount of information I have to receive every day.	
IO3	Usually, my problem is too much information to make a decision.	
IO4	I feel confused by the amount of information I have to take in every day.	
Digital Workplace Stress		
DWS1	I feel exhausted from my digital workplace activities.	[14]] [4] [5]
DWS2	I feel tired of activities that require me to use digital workplace technology.	
DWS3	Working all day with digital workplace technology is a burden for me.	
DWS4	I feel my work is getting harder because I have to use various digital applications simultaneously.	
Mental Health		
MH1	I feel anxious if I don't use social media.	[14]]
MH2	I find it hard to relax if I don't use social media.	

MH3	I feel sad and restless if I don't use social media.	[12]
MH4	I have trouble sleeping due to emotional stress or excessive thinking.	[10]